

S14 - Figure Supplementary Appendix pytools_ARD_ancestralHabitatStates

S4 Supplementary Appendix, S4 - Bayesian Tree

6.0

S6, Supplementary Appendix, S6 - DEC Stochastic Mapping

S13 - Supplementary Appendix, Lineages through time

a) Lineages-through-time plot for *Bicyclus*

b) Lineages-through-time plot for Clade I

c) Lineages-through-time plot for Clade II

Time in million years before present (Ma)

Time from present to the oldest root in Ma